

From third space to shared space

A speculative renovation of university role architecture

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The “third space” refers not to a spatial environment with physical boundaries, but to an imagined location for university work that resists traditional categorisation. Celia Whitchurch (2008) proposed “space” as a metaphor to help us situate practices that otherwise don’t belong within the (also metaphorical) bounds of academic or professional work.

This simple thought experiment took the space metaphor and used it as a basis for speculatively renovating the architecture of work roles in the university. It drew on theoretical work in social science and architecture, and from emerging speculative approaches to inquiry. Speculative methods enable us to contemplate “conditions which may not yet currently exist, to provoke new ways of thinking and to bring particular ideas or issues into focus” (Ross, 2017, p. 215).

Speculative fiction has previously been used to great effect in third space research. Costello et al. (2022) use it to generate profiles of imaginary learning design “superheroes”.

This event took place in two ways: first, as a collaborative mural that participants could add to throughout the asynchronous slowposium, and second as a live presentation during the symposium itself.

Part 1: The Slowposium mural

An online mural hosted on Miro was open for participant contributions over the two weeks of the slowposium. Participants were invited to visualise the “third space” as a material environment, somehow existing in between or alongside the “first” and “second spaces of academic and professional work. They were asked to imagine:

What if there were no boundary between academic or professional work? What if, instead of seeking definition for a liminal third space, we could inhabit a single shared space?

Step 1: Illustrate the third space based on their experience of it.

Participants depicted their own metaphor of the space in relation to the supposed “first” and “second” spaces. Where are the boundaries and/or intersections? Where would your own work take place? Can you see into or enter other spaces? Why did you picture the space this way?

For example:

Figure 1. Towers and tunnels

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Academic work (the medieval tower in Figure 1) is prestigious but archaic, seeming out of touch with the modern world. Professional work (the skyscraper) provides the contemporary business sensibilities that enable academia to turn a profit.

The third space is an underground tunnel between the spaces, where covert collaborations happen. Without these collaborations, neither academic nor professional work could succeed – but they deliberately take place out of view.

Step 2: Renovate the space.

Participants chose one of the illustrations depicted in the first step, and considered: how could this space be altered (now or in the past) to enable any type of university work to happen across spaces?

Participants speculatively altered the dimensions of this space, removing the limits to enable free movement throughout. This took forms like:

- breaking down boundaries
- removal of partition walls
- addition of windows and doors
- construction of a bridge
- a complete demolition making way for a new shared space.

For example:

Figure 2. Tower renovation plan

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Remove the secret tunnel and install ramps, stairways, elevators, slides and ladders between the two spaces, enabling various forms of practical and playful movement between them (Figure 2).

Step 3: Reflect on the feeling of this new shared space.

Participants considered: how might inhabiting it make us feel? What kind of atmosphere might it evoke? What are the potential issues and consequences of the changes – for example:

Who benefits?

What new problems are created?

What would roles look like?

What would work look like?

What might be gained or lost?

Part 2: The symposium presentation

During the symposium itself, I spoke a little more about the ideas behind this speculative project:

You don't go to a third space to do your work. You go to an academic space or a professional space, and you try to fit. But you're always a few toes out of line. You're not home. You do what you can, and then you move into the other space, and it's the same. You're needed, but maybe you're not quite recognised. You're still not home.

As Lakoff and Johnson (1981) famously argued, the metaphors we use shape our understandings of the world around us and the options for action we believe are available to us. For this reason, metaphor can help us speculate on possibilities for change. It is also a way of temporarily disconnecting us from the admin and technicalities of the empirical world.

I wanted to reflect on that metaphor of “space” using the concept of social topologies (Law & Singleton, 2005; Mol & Law, 1994) to suggest a few ways of conceptualising this social construct of work-as-space. These are each potential ways of reimagining the space we currently picture as made up of distances, regions and boundaries. In brief:

- when we think of social space as networked, instead of distance and borders separating us, we’re concerned with who we are connected to and who are aren’t
- when we think of social space as fluid, we think of shifting relationships, borders melting and moving, every part of the space being moved by every other
- when we think of fire space, we think of dynamics that can change instantly, without seeming to move at all.

Fire spaces, flickering rapidly between states of presence and absence, are particularly resonant for those of us operating in digitally mediated university spaces (Gravett et al., 2023). Metaphors like these enable us to visualise social configurations and relationships in their complexity, ambiguity and continuous evolution.

These metaphors are useful insofar as they help us think about social dynamics as a “where”. One of the most obvious examples of networked space is the organisational chart, which maps out where everyone sits in a company, indicating the power structures, the connections between teams, the dotted lines that tell you someone serves two masters. But this is exactly the kind of model that creates binaries and discomfort for those whose work doesn’t fit in (or under) a box. Networked space with its nodes and links is too tidy, too theoretically comfortable, to really describe the shiftingness of the atmosphere we’re trying to describe.

I also wanted to draw on the notion of “affective atmospheres” to contemplate the experience of inhabiting metaphorical spaces. Atmospheres emerge through the assembling of bodies in a space, but cannot be reduced to the simple addition of the former to the latter (Anderson, 2009; Bille et al, 2015). Architectural theory understands atmosphere as a quality linked to how built environments are designed and experienced by those who inhabit them (Sumartojo & Pink, 2018). A medieval church, a marbled hotel lobby, a cramped bedsit each evoke particular feelings in us when we enter them.

I offered a few illustrations of my own as suggestions for how a third space might manifest in fluid, networked and fire topologies.

Figure 3. Third space bubbles in a beaker separating academic from professional fluids

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In the beaker (Figure 3), I imagined academic and professional spaces as something like oil and water: theoretically incompatible, but when they are thrown together, capsules of fluid are formed that might be substantively one, yet enveloped in the other and floating between the two, eventually—inevitably—to be subsumed by the element that dominates.

Figure 4. *A third space elevator moving between professional and academic floors*

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In the building (Figure 4), I pictured the third space as the shaft of a lift that moves between allocated floors. It's not a habitable environment—rather, it's a utility space, a transport zone, designed specifically for people that need to be somewhere else.

Figure 5. A dialogue box appears inviting us to enter a third space in our browser

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When I think of fire space, the first thing that comes to mind is the computer screen (Figure 5). I think of tabs, dialog boxes: things that jump into existence on our monitors, and just as instantly disappear as we choose “ok” or “cancel”. I think of the kind of code-switching work that people must do invisibly when navigating multiple cultures, constantly watching for cues that tell them which version of themselves to be today.

What I really wanted to ask was this: what kind of materials are we actually trying to play with when we think about the architecture of third space? Spaces, their materials, their shapes, and their inhabitants, create affective atmospheres which are shared and which affect who and how we are within them. How do such imaginaries make us feel about the spaces we inhabit and move between? What new imaginaries might we create – and how might we shape them in ways that support our work, each other, and ourselves?

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